

Use of RFID Technology in Libraries

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Area of the Paper : Education Management

Type of the Paper : Exploratory Research

Type of Review : Peer Reviewed as per COPE guidelines

Indexed In : Proquest

How to Cite this Paper:

Namdas V., Naik M. (2023).

Use of RFID Technology in Libraries

Journal of Management Research

XV(2), 81-91 <https://cimr.in/faculty-research.html#research-Journals>

Paper Submission : 30/July/2023

Paper Publication : 30/September/2023

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ABSTRACT

Libraries are the knowledge hubs that collect, organize, preserve and provide access to a wide range of information resources including books, journals, magazines, databases, e-resources, etc. and this information is accessed by the patrons as and when needed by them.

In the pre-computer era, there were manual cataloging cards to find or locate any books in the library. Manual accession register, punch card equipment for circulation of books, etc. However, as the evolution took place, the libraries started automating. Traditional library activities and services are moving to automation. Libraries can optimize their resource management, streamline operations, and enhance patron experiences. RFID enables libraries to evolve into more efficient and user-centric institutions, empowering librarians to focus on providing value-added services while offering patrons a seamless and enjoyable library experience.

Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology has emerged as a transformative solution in the field of library management, revolutionizing traditional systems and procedures. The adoption and impact of RFID technology in libraries, investigating its role in enhancing resource management and patron services.

This research paper covers the Introduction of RFID technology in libraries, application of RFID technology in libraries along with its components, implementation of RFID technology in libraries, advantage and disadvantages of RFID technology in libraries and security concerns related to RFID systems.

Keywords: RFID, Libraries, Data, Security, Technology, Patrons, Tags.

INTRODUCTION OF RFID TECHNOLOGY IN LIBRARIES

Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology was traced back to World War II when radar technology was used to identify and track aircrafts. The first patent of the RFID was registered by Mario W. Cardullo in 1973 for an active RFID transponder. This was the formal beginning of RFID technology.

Worldwide, companies and industries like retail, logistics, supply chain management etc. have adopted RFID technology to improve their inventory management system and to prevent theft loss. One of the successful completion of RFID applications is the toll collection where RFID tags are attached to vehicles to enable automated toll payment systems as they pass through toll booths.

Over the past decades, libraries have played a crucial role in the institutions, serving as a warehouse of knowledge and information. In the modern world the technology has brought tremendous change in every field. Libraries are also adapting to the change that is occurring due to the technology. The latest technology that has been developed in the field of libraries is Radio Frequency Identification (RFID). RFID technology has brought a creative and effective way to manage resources and have completely changed how libraries used to work before.

RFID technology helps to reduce the time required for the stock verification process by the staff. It also identifies misplaced books or wrongly shelved books by the patrons. The middleware software of RFID technology can be linked with the library software (ILMS), which will help for the faster circulation of books. It allows library staff to efficiently manage library collection and circulation tasks, tracking usage of patrons and empowers patron with self-checkout options.

APPLICATIONS OF RFID TECHNOLOGY IN LIBRARIES

RFID technology has electromagnetic fields to identify and track objects that are equipped with RFID tags. There are microchips in every RFID tag which store data in digital form. These chips also contain antennas which help to transmit the data. An item which is RFID tagged is scanned by the RFID reader, then the reader encodes the information stored in the tag and facilitates quick and accurate identification of the item. Below mentioned components are the key applications of the RFID Technology in libraries.

COMPONENTS OF RFID TECHNOLOGY

RFID technology comprises three essential components: RFID tags and antennas, RFID readers, and a Backend & Database. There are some other components that are optionally used for functioning of RFID technology.

1. RFID Tags and Antennas:

RFID tags consist of small electronic circuits that store data and emit radioactive waves to communicate with tags, capturing the transmitted data and forwarding it to the computer system for processing. The RFID tag holds unique identification data, which could be a serial number, a product code, or other relevant information.

The antenna on the RFID tag is responsible for transmitting and receiving radio frequency signals. It allows the tag to communicate with RFID readers.

Once the RFID tag is activated, the data is stored in its memory. The RFID tags have inbuilt memory that can store additional data beyond the unique identifier. The data written on the memory can be rewritable.

In libraries, RFID tags are attached to library materials like books, journals, DVDs, and other items to streamline various processes and to enhance user experience. RFID-enabled student ID cards will help to prove the identity of the student and also help for quick circulation of library materials.

2. RFID Readers:

RFID readers are devices equipped with antennas that emit radio frequency signals and receive responses from RFID tags in their range. The RFID reader may be in the form of a portable device or permanently attached to a connected network.

When an RFID tag is within the range of an RFID reader, the reader sends out a radio frequency signal that powers the tag.

The powered tag then responds to the reader's signal by transmitting its stored data back to the

reader. The reader captures the information from the tag and forwards it to the backend system for processing and further actions.

3. Backend Database referred as “Middleware Software”:

The Backend Database or the middleware software consists of databases that manage the data collected from RFID tags.

When an RFID tag is read by an RFID reader, the data is sent to the middleware software, where it can be stored, analyzed and utilized for various applications.

The middleware software can be integrated with other library management systems, allowing for seamless incorporation of RFID data into existing library operations.

There are some other optional components that can be used for RFID technology in libraries.

1. Handheld Reader:

Handheld readers are the portable devices which are used to read RFID tags from a specific distance that are put on the library materials. The handheld reader has antennas that produce radio waves that transmit signals to detect the RFID tag. Once the RFID tag is detected, the tag sends back waves through the antenna where it is generated into data. It is mainly used for quick stock verification of the library material. It also helps to find out any misplaced library books or materials. Handheld readers are optimized with Windows or Android operating systems which are pre-installed. Latest version of the handheld reader has a touch screen that supports android applications with inbuilt Wi-Fi.

2. Staff Station Reader:

Staff Station Reader is like a flat panel device which can be placed at the issue/return counter for quick circulation of library materials. Staff station reader performs various operations such as RFID tagging, reading information from RFID tags like patrons' information or book information, issuing of library materials to the patrons, handling return of large numbers of library materials in one single go. It also performs stock verification tasks. The staff station reader serves as a centralized tool for library staff to carry out tasks more efficiently and effectively.

3. Kiosk System - Self Service:

A kiosk system is a terminal installed outside the library premises where patrons can perform various tasks independently without direct assistance by the library staff. Kiosk system reduces the patrons waiting line process and saves the time to return library materials. The 24/7 accessibility of kiosks can be available outside the regular business hours, providing patrons with access to services and information at any time. This improves the patron's satisfaction.

4. RFID Label Printer:

RFID label printer is a specialized printer designed to create adhesive labels that is used to cover the RFID tags. To safeguard RFID tags, it is advisable to affix protective labels containing printed instructions to the patrons like 'Avoid removing the RFID tag' or 'Do not peel out the RFID tag etc.

5. Anti-Theft detection - RFID Gate:

Anti-Theft gates are basically security gates which are used to prevent theft of the library materials. The theft detection machine detects unauthorized access of library materials to take outside the library premises or which are not issued by the library staff. If any patron takes out

library material without issuing it, an alarm triggers and alerts the library staff. This technology helps in preventing loss of library materials.

IMPLEMENTATION OF RFID IN LIBRARIES

RFID implementation in libraries has proven to be a transformative step towards modernizing and optimizing library operations. The integration of RFID technology involves several key stages and considerations to ensure successful deployment and utilization.

a. Planning and Need Assessment:

Librarians should plan and assess the need for RFID technology in libraries and what all benefits occur after implementing the RFID technology in libraries.

b. Selection of RFID Technology:

Librarians must select appropriate RFID systems according to their requirements and budget constraints.

c. Tagging of Library Materials:

Librarians should decide which library resources should be tagged by the RFID. In the initial stage it can be partially implemented on the books and later it should be implemented on all library materials.

d. System Integration and Compatibility with ILMS (Integrated Library Management System):

It's essential to consider how the RFID components, software, and existing systems will integrate and interact. Working with vendors and experts who understand library system integration and compatibility can help to ensure a successful RFID implementation that aligns with the library's needs and goals.

e. Data Migration:

The current library data needs to migrate into the RFID middleware software including item records, patron information, and circulation history and needs to be synchronized with the existing ILMS.

f. Staff Training:

Library staff should be given proper training on how to use and maintain RFID technology in libraries.

g. Patron Orientation:

Librarians should educate patrons or display steps on the library website page about how to use RFID technology and should get familiar with the self return kiosk system and any other RFID related features.

h. Pilot testing:

Before full scale implementation of RFID technology in libraries, pilot testing should be carried out. Identify any operational challenges, if everything is fine then libraries can move forward to implement RFID.

i. Full Implementation:

Once testing is done, Librarians can start rolling out of RFID Technology across the library environment.

j. Maintenance and Support:

Regular maintenance of RFID should be essential for its smooth functioning. Libraries should take AMC for any software updates or any technical issues that occur.

ADVANTAGE AND DISADVANTAGES OF RFID TECHNOLOGY IN LIBRARIES

RFID technology offers a large number of benefits to libraries, transforming traditional library operations into modernization of library services and significantly enhancing overall efficiency of libraries and patron services.

Some of the advantages of RFID Technology in libraries include:

- Efficient self-service issue/return processes.
- Quick and accurate library stock checks.
- Automation saves staff time for more valuable tasks.
- Reduction in errors from manual data entry.
- Enhanced security with RFID gates and tags.
- Empowerment of patrons through self-service kiosks.
- Improved accessibility services for diverse needs.
- Data analytics insights for informed decision-making.
- Personalized recommendations for patrons.
- Optimized collection management and shelving.
- Efficient returns handling with RFID-enabled book drops.
- Targeted promotions and engagement through kiosks.
- Shorter queues and reduced wait times for patrons.
- Overall enhanced patron experience and modernized operations.

By embracing RFID technology, libraries can revolutionize their operations, enhance patron experiences, and adapt to the evolving needs of their communities, positioning themselves as modern and user-centric information hubs.

DISADVANTAGES OF RFID TECHNOLOGY IN LIBRARIES

Though RFID Technology offers various benefits, there are some disadvantages that are to be considered while implementing RFID technology in libraries.

- High initial investment costs for equipment and installation.
- Complex integration with existing library management systems.
- Privacy concerns due to potential unauthorized access to patron data.
- Security vulnerabilities if not properly protected from hacking.
- Potential for tag failures and reading errors.
- Need for staff training on RFID technology usage.
- Ongoing maintenance costs for updates and repairs.
- Requirement for technical expertise to manage and troubleshoot.
- Possibility of radio frequency interference affecting tag reading.
- Time-consuming tag application process.
- Different tag types required for various materials.

- Incompatibility with certain item types (e.g., metal-covered).
- RFID tag performance affected by environmental conditions.
- Resistance to change from patrons and staff.

SECURITY AND PRIVACY CONCERNS

While RFID technology offers numerous benefits to libraries, it also raises legitimate security and privacy concerns that need to be addressed to ensure the protection of patron data and the integrity of library systems. Some of the key security and privacy concerns associated with RFID implementation in libraries include:

- Unauthorized access to sensitive data on RFID tags.
- Risk of hackers intercepting RFID signals.
- Potential data breaches compromising patron information.
- Possibility of tag cloning leading to impersonation.
- Vulnerability to malware and virus attacks.
- Risk of eavesdropping on tag-reader communication.
- Privacy issues when storing sensitive data on tags.
- Exposure of data to third-party vendors.
- Lack of user consent for data collection.
- Identity theft due to exposed personal data.
- Need for compliance with data protection regulations.

CONCLUSION

RFID technology has emerged as a transformative change in the field of libraries, revolutionizing the way resources are managed, and services are delivered. The implementation of RFID technology has led to significant improvements in circulation efficiency, inventory management (stock verification), and patron experiences. By automating routine tasks and enabling self-service options, RFID has freed up valuable staff time, allowing librarians to focus on more personalized interactions and specialized services.

In addition, RFID technology's ability to track items in real-time has made libraries more secure by reducing theft and unauthorized access to materials. As libraries adapt to using digital resources, the possibility of combining RFID with technologies like IoT, mobile apps, and biometrics brings exciting potential for creating a smooth and connected library experience.

Yet, just like any technology, introducing RFID also brings up worries about security and privacy that need careful attention. Strong protection methods, teaching users, and clear data rules are important to keep patron information safe and maintain patron's confidence in the library.

In the end, RFID technology in libraries represents a promising and powerful tool that empowers librarians, enhances patron experiences, and paves the way for a bright and innovative future for the library ecosystem.

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